

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B116
Date: 26 Jul 2005
Take Off: 10:02:24Z
Landing: 15:03:16Z
Flight Time: 5h02m52s

Campaign: UTLS Cirrus 7

Operating Area: SW Approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Ian Ramsey-Rae	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	Manchester University
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	CCM2/Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	Core chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	CCN / AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University
9	ADA/CPI	Paul Connolly	Manchester University
10	WAS	Ruth Boddy	University of York
11	PTRMS	Anne Hulse	UEA
12	PTRMS Training	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
13	NOxy	Andy MacDonald	UEA
14	PAN	Jim Hopkins	UEA
15	Observer	Steve Ball	FAAM
16	Observer	Gareth Mitchell	BBC Radio 4
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b116
 Date: 26th July, 05
 Project: Cirrus
 Location: Cornwall

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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085912		Start posn	0.36 kft	126	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
093753		INU	0.36 kft	126	Set to Navigate
100224		T/O	0.93 kft	033	Cranfield
100824		ASPs	8.3 kft	359	Open
101012		NOXY	10.0 kft	184	Cals
101737		Videos	10.0 kft	245	Start RFC & RFC
105616	105827	Profile 1	15.0 - 17.0 kft	215	1000fpm ATC Interrupt
110111	110634	Profile 1	17.0 - 21.0 kft	062	
110844	111942	Profile 1	21.0 - 30.0 kft	231	Interrupt
111815		EVM	29.3 kft	234	500fpm from FL290
112744	113048	Profile 1	30.0 - 32.0 kft	056	
113314	113612	Profile 1	32.0 - 33.1 kft	227	
113734	114749	Run 1	33.0 kft	239	Above Ci
113801		Video	33.0 kft	243	Restart RFC(chewed)
115011	120012	Run 2	32.1 - 32.0 kft	048	
120225	121226	Run 3	31.0 kft	227	JW & Nevz calcs
121649	122624	Run 4	30.0 kft	054	
122904	123905	Run 5	29.0 kft	237	JW & Nevz calcs
124305	125306	Run 6	28.0 kft	064	JW & Nevz calcs
125615	130615	Run 7	27.1 - 27.0 kft	232	
131039	132041	Run 8	26.1 - 26.0 kft	049	JW & Nevz calcs
131250		Video	26.0 kft	055	Change FFC tape
132301	133404	Run 9	25.1 - 25.0 kft	250	
134230	135232	Run 10	24.0 kft	080	Ci base
135515	140516	Run 11	23.0 kft	243	JW & Nevz calcs
141058	142506	Run 12	21.0 kft	033	Below Ci
143342		NOxy	10.1 kft	075	Cals
145030		ASPs	7.4 kft	060	Close
150316		Land	0.39 kft	342	Cranfield
150853		Stop posn	0.39 kft	309	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B116 Track 26-JUL-05

6°W 5°W 4°W 3°W 2°W 1°W 0°

Sortie Brief UTLS CIRRUS 7 (Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1)

Flight Number B116

Date 16th July 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To make measurements of the microphysics of cirrus clouds and of their interaction with local aerosol and oxides of nitrogen. To investigate the effects of precipitation from the cloud on the vertical distribution of aerosol and oxidized nitrogen

Sortie Location: SW approaches in layers of cirrus ahead of approaching front

Sortie Summary: The aircraft will initially make a vertical profile from well below cloud base to above the top of the cirrus. It will then make a series of straight and level runs (SLRs) of 10 mins duration at several altitudes below, in and, when possible, above the cloud top. The straight and level runs above and below cloud will concentrate on determining the gaseous composition and aerosol physical and chemical properties of the air. Measurements of the vertical wind velocity will be made here. A straight and level run will be made very close to cloud base to determine whether supercooled water droplets or ice crystals are being activated. Runs progressively deeper into the cloud will then be flown. SLRs will also be made in the fall streaks from the cirrus to characterise the precipitation in this region and to investigate the influence of the evaporation of the precipitation on the aerosol properties and trace gases in the region of the fall streaks. Advantage will also be taken to fly in and make measurements of any aircraft contrails (and fall streaks from contrails) found in the region (same approach as for natural Ci) .

Sortie Detail

- a. T+0 Take off and climb to FL100 for transit to operating area (with appropriate time [~20mins] - spent at FL100 for NO_x calibration)
- b. T+40 Perform vertical profile ascent P1 through cirrus from below cloud base to aircraft ceiling (fuel load dependant), or to above Ci top whichever is the lower (1000ft/min).
- c. T+60 Descend (not profile descent) to below base of cirrus generating cells and perform straight and level run (SLR) parallel to the mean wind direction 300 feet below cloud base for 10 minutes.
- d. T+75 Turn through 180 degrees. Ascend to cloud base and perform straight and level run for 10 minutes just in cloud at the base of the generating cells. Deviations from the straight run may be made in order to penetrate generating cells provided such penetrations can be achieved with wings level.
- e. T+90 Turn through 180 degrees ascend to middle of cloud and perform SLR for 10 min
- f. T+105 Turn through 180 degrees and if possible ascend to above cloud top and perform straight and level run duration 10 minutes above cloud top
- g. T+120 Descend to below cirrus base and make level runs through fall streaks adjusting flight path to pass through fall streaks as required.
- h. T+135 Descend to lowest altitude reached by fall streaks and make and level runs through the residue.
(NB order of SLRs c-h may be changed by mission scientist to h-c if considered appropriate)
- i. Repeat items b to h as time permits (including profile P2 to above P1 ceiling if failed to get above cloud top in P1)
- j. T+260 return transit (with appropriate time spent at appropriate altitude for NO_x cal)
- k. T+300 Land

Sortie Title UTLS Cirrus 7 (Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry Option 1)

Scientific Aims:

1. To measure the total number of Condensation Nuclei (CN), CCN, IN* and the size distribution of optically active particles in clean and polluted air in the UTLS region over the UK. Assessment of their spatial distribution and their likely source based on tracer measurements and air mass history.
2. To quantify the extent to which air mass history, and gas and particle loading can affect the microphysical properties of cirrus clouds in the UTLS region, in particular, the size distribution, phase and morphology of cloud particles.
3. To obtain estimates of HNO₃ loss to cirrus clouds and the subsequent effect on the aerosol population after the cloud has evaporated using case studies involving one or more wave clouds.
4. To make observations of the number, size distribution, phase and morphology of droplets and crystals in cirrus cloud and the number and size distribution of interstitial particles and correlate these with measurements of tracers that identify anthropogenic influence. Hence building on objective 3 to investigate the influence of cirrus on the distribution of aerosol and gases in the UTLS region as cloud and precipitation evaporate.
5. To make an assessment of the chemical composition of the particulate in the UTLS region as a function of their size, their spatial variability and the effect different sources have on their composition.
6. To use measurements of the masses of key components as a function of size of cirrus particle dry residues and interstitial particles to determine if there are distinct chemical differences between activated and unactivated particles.
7. To establish the partitioning of oxidised nitrogen between the gas and aerosol phases as a function of air mass history and source region

Weather conditions

Cirrus cloud preferably associated with the polar front jet preferably over the UK.

Key Measurements

All instruments to be operated continuously.

1) Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 and SID-2*. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits etc.
- ADA/CPI – as above
- CCN - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample per run, if possible.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- TWC – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

2) FWVS – Switch off the lamp when frost point rises above -15C. Calibration should be performed following altitude changes.

3) WAS - 2 bottle samples per 10min flight leg unless otherwise notified by the Mission Scientist.

- 4) AMS - to be operated on Rosemount inlet. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.
- 5) Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rear. Flight manager or Flight Scientists should monitor rearward video and inform Mission Scientist of any occurrences of contrail formation (or cessation) and these should be noted in log sheets.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER

CIRRUS 7

Flight No **B116**.....

Date 26/07/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:02:25	BST 14MB				T/O
					CB Sc 2000' ~ 200' thick
					CB 3500' ~ 300-400' thick
					Main CB ~ 5500' CT ~ 7500'
10:10:25	Cals	FL100			NO ₂ cal stat
10:11:35	Cals	FL100	234	52.3N/0.6W	2.5°C/-24.6°C 9m/s/283° 696mb 247kt
10:19:30	= 11:19:34	BST KNB			TIME CHECK
					17-18000' CB above us ALF-estimated
10:21:30	Cals	FL100	245	52.0/1.5W	2.4°C/-24.0°C 8m/s/280° 696mb 253
10:25:20		FL100			CEN ready to sample
10:27:50	Cals	FL100	252	51.9/2.2W	NO ₂ Cals complete
10:33:56					Photo 1 LMS Bank, RMS. Photo 2
10:39	Ascent				Ascending to 15000'
			235	51.5/3.6W	Cloud above very thin
10:42:49	Level	FL150	235	51.5/3.7W	-7.44/-33.7°C 5m/s/277° 571mb 276kt
10:48:40					CEN not working well - knock it on head.
10:51:30					ORC = 150 CPC _{arms} = 1000 ?
10:56:17	PI stat	FL150-170			CI ahead (along N coast Canada - looks thinner)
					CI south also looks thin ? best under
10:58:10				50.6/4.5W	where we just came from
10:58:26	PI mt	F170	216		-10.89/-10.28° 7m/s/237° 527mb 283kt
10:01:10	PI recovery				ie we are into cloud (stratus) - over coast
11:04:00	PI		57°	50.6/4.5	CT on LMS ~ 150 - cloud to RMS
11:06:33	PI mt	F210			gathered some LWC on a/c detectors - debris

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWEN

CIRCUITS 7

Flight No **B.116**.....

Date 26/07/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:08:00		FL210			650, 720 CPC's same
11:08:44	P1 rec	from FL210	234	50.7, 4.1W	(heading West)
11:10:40					(Photo ⁴ LMS) - Ci very inhom - some blurring on wings - others not!
11:11:20	P1	23800			2DC low Cirrus - picking ice - poly Xroads CPI
11:13:50	P1	25800	234	50.4/4.6W	-28.38 / -27.35°C 364mb 21/234°
					No IWC - Cloud Phys / CPI - nev3
11:15:45	P1	27100			-32.18 / -30.83 338mb 22/230° 334kt
11:17:40	P1	29000	234		2DC - 60/l. 200µm - mixed
					-36.54 / -37.33 312mb
11:18:10	P1				Cloud reduced to 500'/min.
11:19:39	P1 stop	FL300	234	50.2/50.1	Distinct cloud layer 21m/s/213 -39.98/-39.04
				(Photo) ←	LH Turn - looks like very heads of CT
					CPI - looks B Rossiter
11:23:18	land.	FL300	00	50.1/4.8W	-39.06 / -39.81 300mb 358kts 21/227°
					seem to be heading into cloud
11:24:47					CPC 500 CMC - 10000 - 0000
					(held at FL300 by ATC)
11:25:50					Photo 5, 6, 7. CT. start ahead
11:26:52				50.4/4.2	(in and out of CT.) -39.7 / -38.46 300mb
					A/C 3000' above us was contrailing
11:27:43	P1 recon	from FL300	56	50.5/4.1	← CONTRAIL - went right through it
11:28:34	P1				CPI - did not see contrail - CPC pulsed - ^{We are} contrailing
11:30:40	P1 int	FL300	NHT	50.6/3.7	-44.57 / -42.9° 31m/s/223 274mb 353kts
					Planes LMS - 38000 - Not contrailing
11:33:13	P1 recon	FL320-330	230	50.5/3.6	500/min

Mission Scientist's Log

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Flight No **B. N6**.....

Date 26/07/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:34:28	P1	32400	231	50.5/3.7	CT Whusps
11:35:30	P1	32700	232	50.4/3.7	CT proceeds. ✓ 33m/s 239 264mb
✓ 11:36:10	P1 end	33000	232	50.4/3.8	-46.94/-46.47°C 261mb 34m/s/239° 338kts
11:37:33	R1 st	FL330	242	50.4/4.0	
11:39:10	R1				Rounded bottom - old con trail
11:40:00	R1				- short columns, plates - poly X'tals - small 100µm
11:40:15	R1				Core Chem done - cuts - WAS
11:41:34	R1	FL330	243	50.2/4.4	-47.28/-47.37 34m/s 239° 261mb
11:42:12	R1				into cloud again
11:46:40	R1	FL330			into cloud again
11:47:26					Contrail - dropping from above -
11:47:47	R1 end	FL330	244	50.0/5.1	261 -47.51/-46.84° - R47
		FL320			CPI - rosettes again
11:50:11	R2 st	FL320	54	50.1/5.1	-44.57/-43.47° 26m/s/228 273mb 341kts
					patches of mistier air - patchy contrails.
11:53:20					(not LWC - ice - CPI)
12:00:12	R2 end	FL320		50.6/3.7	
12:02:25	R3 st	FL310		gamy mist	Contrails - patchy mist remains again
12:05:56	R3	FL310	241	50.6/3.9W	-41.8/-40.91 286mb 31m/s/239° 336kts
12:12:25	R3 end	FL310	241	50.4/4.6W	-41.93/41.12° 31/231° 287mb
12:14:20		FL300			CPI had to reboot - back on-line
12:15:48	R4	FL300	59	50.4/4.9	-39.15/-36.73 300mb 24m/s/225°
					NB SO ₂ in Plots is O ₃ today - O ₃ is U/S
12:22:50	R4	FL300	57		cloud free zone - cloud below + above
12:24:23	R4				- poly X'tals - short columns but plates

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B...116**.....

 Date **26/07/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:26:22					position columns/v later now
12:26:24	R4end	FL 300	SZ	51.0/35W	- will do just 1 bottle on this leg
12:29:03	R5st	FL 290	230	50.9/35	-36.67/-37.47, 314mb 26m/s/241° 318kt
12:35:48	R5	FL 290		50	double layer structure again
12:32:05	R5end	FL 290	236	50.5/45	35.99/35.93 ↓ 27/229°
12:43:06	R6st	FL 280	60	50.4/43	-33.61/-31.69 21m/s/230 328mb 323kt
					[Contour ^{from} at 4000' above us FL320]
12:50:52	R6	FL 280	S6	50.8/34	Contour above again on this NE (grey) leg.
12:52:31	R6	FL 280			CNC ~ 165
12:53:04	R6end	FL 280	S6	50.9/3.1	-33.8/-34.5 °C 23/242° 329mb.
					CPC ~ 700 (AMS) → discrepancy again
12:54:40	land	FL 270			-31.14/-30.78 343mb 31m/s/248° 305kt
12:56:13	R7st	FL 270			going SW
13:00:50	R7	FL 270	233	50.7/3.3W	50 Whit max 400µm BR. etc.
13:06:15	R7end	FL 270	236	50.4/3.8W	-30.89/-30.44 343mb 24m/s/240 314kt
13:10:38	R8st	FL 260		going	359mb -28.72/-28.93 20mk/241° 304kt
13:12:54	R8	FL 260	55	50.5/3.5W	more poly Xtrals - max like around C -
					2DC - seeing good bullet residuals - CPI seeing
13:13:52	R8	FL 260			poly crystals 1 WAS bottle from ... Now!
13:18:20	R8	FL 260			At can see out of CB - see lower level cloud
13:20:41	R8end	FL 260		51.0/2.7W	
13:22:59	R9st	FL 250	249°	50.9/2.7W	Going SW again -26.63/-27.65° 24m/s/249°
					CPI - more rounded poly Xtrals - submarking
					2DC - grouped !! - CB visible on RMS
13:27:24	R9	FL 250	249	50.8/3.2	-26.62°/-27.46° 21m/s/244° 375mb

33 2
32 4
31 0
30 6
29 10 8
28 12 6
27 14 4
26 16 2

hr left.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER

CARRUS 7

Flight No **B.116**.....

Date 26/07/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:13:23	R9	FL250	249	50.7/3.7W	20 m/s / 241° -27.03/-26.65°C 304kt 375mb running a bit longer on this run.
13:34:04	R9 end	FL250	249	50.7/3.9W	as above - continuing at this altitude
13:37:45	descending				low N ₂ - large / small X ₂ als - sharp edged poly X ₂ als -
13:40:23	Turn	FL240		50.5/4.6W	L1 turn - CPI X ₂ als are now sublimated Rather diffuse CB - but in turn I can also see some blue sky - so layer is thinner here.
13:42:30	R10 st	FL240	75°	50.4/4.4W	-24.82°C/-24.62°C 392mb 297kt 16mb/23° big sublimated ice X ₂ als - with odd burst of sharp X ₂ als.
13:52:31	R10 end	FL240		50.6/3.1	-24.78/-25.28°C 392mb 17m/s/234°
13:55:15	R11 st	FL230	245°	50.6/3.1W	409mb -22.45/-22.61, 16m/s/240° 294kt CPI small patches some large sharp edged poly X ₂ als 600-400µm, 2DC peak 150µm ⁻¹ generally 30µm ⁻¹
14:05:14	R11 end	FL230		50.4/4.1	- turning N - to get across from front - maintaining altitude - maybe CB further N is higher
14:08:36		FL230-210			- Yes - descending to FL210.
14:09:25					R. Turn to Brecon
14:10:56	R12	FL210			CPI X ₂ als very rounded - sublimated
14:12:06	R12	FL210		50.7.4.1W	-18.5°C/-20.03°C 465mb 12m/s/229° 281kt
14:15:53					Last WAS bottle filled.
14:25:06	R12 end				

SO₂ correction

S102 -
PARS

CPI -
CNC CCN.

[CB - 7200' on return]
[CB - 6400']

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B116

Date : 26 Jul 2005

Operator and contact info : Doug Anderson (dougan@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	No problems
O₃	Old O3 instrument U/S and not on board. New O3 instrument is fitted in SO2 bay and logged to RAW SO2 parameter on HORACE
NO_x	No problems
SO₂	U/S – not on board
TDLAS	Not operated
WAS	

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick cals) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
09:41:18	Ground	
10:14:03	FL100	Lamp temp a little low, fixed post cal
11:39:27	FL330	
11:53:12	FL320	
12:05:19	FL310	
12:15:00	FL300	Not full cal, valve check only ~20 sec
12:31:58	FL290	
12:47:00	FL280	
12:57:00	FL270	Not full cal, valve check only ~20 sec
13:13:43	FL260	
13:23:30	FL250	Not full cal, valve check only ~20 sec
13:45:32	FL240	
13:58:21	FL230	
14:11:50	FL210	Not full cal, valve check only ~20 sec
14:22ish	FL200	Cal failed, started another straight away
14:29:01	FL200	Cal OK

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B116

Date: 10/08/05

Operator: papj

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
105616											Start p1
105728	3	0.09	331	0							160
105830	5	0.1	331	0							170
110330	5	0.08	359	0							190
110630	10	0.08	359	0							210
111042	3	0.09	359	10	5	400	4				230
111255	2	0.09	359								250
111405	10	0.1	360	20	5	200	4				260
111516	6	0.09	360	5							270
111630	8	0.1	360	80	60	200	8				280
1118	40	0.6	361	100	50	400	4				290
111930	10	0.1	361	50	40	400	10				300
112909	30	0.3	367	100	60	350	4				310
113047	15	0.1	368	100	40	200	10				320
113612											330 end p1
113734	4	0.3	369	10							Start Run 1
1140	2	0.2	369	40	10	100	11				
1142	20	0.3	369	100	50	100	11				
1144	5	0.08	369	5	1	200	4				
1146	40	0.4	370	500	50	400	4				
114749											End run 1
115011											Start run 2
1157	10	0.3	373	20	10	150	11				
1159	200	0.7	374	100							
120012											End run 2
120225	8	0.08	374								Start run 3
1204	5	0.16	374	5	5	400	4				
1206	8	0.1	375	75	80	150	11				
1208	6	0.1	375	10	5	100	11				
1210	50	0.4	376								
121226	10	0.1									End run 3

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B116

Date: 10/08/05

Operator: papj

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
121649											Start run 4
1218	200	0.08	377	100	50	225	10				
1220	50	0.6	378	100	100	300	10				
1222	900	0.7	379	20	20	400	4				
1224	50	0.4	379	100	20	200	8				
122624	16	0.1	379	100	10	150	11				
122904											Start run 5
12312	20	0.3	381	100	50	225	8				
1233	8	0.1	381	100	10	350	8				
1235	40	0.3	381	100	10	300	4				
1237	10	0.1	382	100	30	300	4				
123905											End run
1246											Start run 6
1313	100	0.3	412	100	20	600	4				
1316	160	0.6	422	400	100	700	4				
1319	70	0.4	425	100	50	300	10				
1321											
132301											Start run 9
1325	20	0.1	428	75	20	375	8				
1327	300	0.7	431	200	100	600	9				
1329	200	0.6	435	100	40	450	8	15000	800	8	
1331	20	0.1	438	100	10	700	8	3500	1000	8	
1333	40	0.2	440	300	50	350	8	15			
133404											End of run 9
134230											Start run 10
1344	15	0.1	453	80	10	600	8				
1346	15	0.1	452	75	5	600	8				
1348	30	0.1	453	75	10	600	8	4000	1000	8	
1350	50	0.4	455	75	10	600					
135232											End run 10

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B116

Date: 26/07/2005

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B116.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B116.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B116.zip		
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B116.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B116_seadas.dat iii) exit		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B116 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B116_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B116 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image		This section is optional

<p>a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B116 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10</p>		
<p>iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files</p>	PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B116_2Dx_IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
<p>9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: B116 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data</p>		
<p>e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B116_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unkown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B116_PROC2D</p>		Note the particle type
<p>10) In PVWAVE</p> <p>i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!</p> <p>ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B116_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B116_M5PROC2D'</p> <p>iii) exit</p>		
<p>11) MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B116_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B116_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B116**Date:** 26/07/2005

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures B116_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) run MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: B116 b) File name: PMSDATA:B116_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:B116_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:B116_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:B116_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: Default = 1 If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here e) Calibration volume flow rate: Use the most recent value. Calibration files to be stored in ????? Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm ³ /sec f) Time correction: Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9 d) g) Start time: 0 if unknown h) End time: 240000 if unknown		Note the min size channel Note the volume flow rate
3) In PVWAVE i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) write_procpcasp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B116_procpcasp.dat' , 'pmsdata:B116_m5procpcasp' iii) exit		
4) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B116_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:B116_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B116
Date: 26/07/2005

Campaign Name: CIRRUS
Operator: R. Boddy (York)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
			Cases 2 and 3 available today. Clock synch at 09:32:50	
~10:02:25			Take off Cranfield	
~10:06:30			Turn on WAS pump & compressed air cylinder	(3.19)
			FL100 - NOxy cals	
~10:40			Ascend to FL450	
~10:43			Level at FL150	
10:56:16			Start profile 1 (ascending from FL150)	(2.92)
10:58:27			Interrupt profile 1 (FL170)	
11:01:11			Recommence profile 1	
11:06:34			Interrupt profile 1 (FL210)	
11:08:44			Recommence profile 1	(2.71)
11:19:42			Interrupt profile 1 (FL300)	
11:27:44			Recommence profile 1	(2.23)
~11:28:23			Sample contrail observed from another aircraft	
11:30:48			Interrupt profile 1 (FL320)	
11:33:14			Recommence profile 1	
11:36:12			End profile 1 (FL330)	
11:37:34			Start run 1 (FL330)	
11:40:30	11:41:30	41	Fast fill 60 s	1.88
11:44:46	11:46:16	42	Fast fill 90 s	2.07
11:47:49			End run 1	
~11:48:45			Descending FL330 to FL320	
11:50:11			Start run 2 (FL320)	
11:53:25	11:54:55	43	Fast fill 90 s	2.13
11:58:01	11:59:31	44	Fast fill 90 s	2.13
12:00:12			End run 2	
12:02:25			Start run 3 (FL310)	
12:05:31	12:07:01	45	Fast fill 90 s	2.21
12:10:00	12:11:30	46	Fast fill 90 s	2.21

12:12:26			End run 3	
12:16:49			Start run 4 (FL300)	
12:19:04	12:20:34	47	Fast fill 90 s	2.27
12:24:06	12:25:36	48	Fast fill 90 s	2.26
12:26:24			End run 4	
12:29:04			Start run 5 (FL290)	
12:32:41	12:33:41	49	Fast fill 60 s	2.18
12:37:03	12:38:03	50	Fast fill 60 s	2.18
12:39:05			End run 5	
12:43:05			Start run 6 (FL280)	
12:47:08	12:48:08	51	Fast fill 60 s	2.26
12:51:25	12:52:25	52	Fast fill 60 s	2.26
12:53:06			End run 6	
12:56:15			Start run 7 (FL270)	
12:58:28	12:59:28	53	Fast fill 60 s	2.41
13:06:15			End run 7	
13:10:39			Start run 8 (FL260)	
13:15:10	13:16:10	54	Fast fill 60 s	2.47
13:20:41			End run 8	
13:23:01			Start run 9 (FL250)	
13:28:01	13:29:01	55	Fast fill 60 s	2.55
13:34:04			End run 9	
13:42:30			Start run 10 (FL240)	
13:52:32			End run 10	
13:55:15			Start run 11 (FL230)	
14:05:16			End run 11	
14:10:58			Start run 12 (FL210)	
14:14:31	14:15:31	56	Fast fill 60 s	2.73
14:25:06			End run 12	
~14:33:36			FL100 - NOxy cals	
~14:48:25			Start descent	
~14:50			Air sample line taps closed	

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 26/07/05

FLIGHT: B116

OPERATOR: Jonny

Tuning

TIME: 0824	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	30	30	22
Def Outer	15	15	11
Heater Bias	-6.87	-6.68	-6.5
Focus	15.5	15	12.5
Extraction	226	230	220

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME: 0830	New	Typical
KV	2.5	n/a
KV Change	0	0.025kV
Gain	3.45e6	3.00E+06
G used Change	1.14	1

TIME: 1514	New	Typical
KV	2.5	n/a
KV Change	0	0.025kV
Gain	2.86	3.00E+06
G used Change	0.83	1

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME: 0843	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.11e-6	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.858	4
IPP NO3	410.5	400
IPP NH4	569.37	550
Airbeam MS	2.54	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	1090611	2.00E+06
Run Number	3643	n/a

TIME: 1534	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	2.212	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.621	4
IPP NO3	514.2	400
IPP NH4	360.40	550
Airbeam MS	2.76	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	2.36	2.00E+06
Run Number	3923	n/a

Filter Run

TIME:	
Run number	

TIME:	
Run number	

CPI Log

26/7/05
Tuesday

B116

1 of 6

CPI on - fine.

ADA on - time copiers to ~400 each
-- drifted down to 375 each

Cal diode

	zero = 10	
	shifted = 316	→ 330
	unshifted = 167	→ 357
	batt = 483	→ 668

Problem with ADA ~~set~~ hardware

error message

"~~has~~ External channel board N/A"

No ADA for this flight

10:06 Droplet cloud with CPI

Profile #1

2 of 6

105616

✓
 Polygraph, through bullet wickets

- 1124 → cpi going wild in low turbulence
 - 1126 a little better now
-
- 1127 heaters seem to be too warm - leave a while to see if goes away.

Resume Profile 1

11:2744 30 kft

- 11:30 turned off pyro & camera filter for heaters. temporarily
- Interrupted @ 113048 32 kft
- 1132 the probe is still going haywire on turbulence

Resume Profile 1 @ 113314 32 kft

seeing plate fans.

1136 - switched heaters back on & panel
went haywire. OK now

End prof 113612

1137 | an going to up min pixel
size to 5. from 4

- 113734 Run 1 @ 33kf-

bullet rosettes etc

Still problems with wallpaper - I am in
trigger mode!

- Turn off heaters to check.
- no improvement
- Increase threshold to 50 from 41
- better now.

End 114749

Run 2 11511 32.1kf

There is a definite pattern with
CPI Nose, Pylon & Camera filter
temp reading - they are @ 62 C (2047 say)

- turn on to see if any different.

All heater readings not working.

~~Page~~
4 of 6

Try rebooting probe after

End 120012

Start m3 12 02 25

Changing CPI settings

End of m3 121226

Start m 4 121645

Rebooted - problem has gone away now

1221 problem has come back

Decided to ignore heater problem and
carry on as normal.

- Pressure crystal now

End m4 122624

Start run 5 ft 290 122909

5 of 6

Some prismatic crystals.

End 123905

Run 6 Start 124305

Plate polycrystals.

End Run 6 125306

Inter view again

Start Run 7 125615 ft 271k ft

Polycrystals

End of Run 7 130615

Start Run 8 26 131032

NB/ ~~we~~ look like at cloud top. ~~is~~
Says Mission Scientist.

Crystals look more like anvil cirrus.

1320 → In cirrus & frame rate is ~40/s

End 132041

Start Run 9 @ 250 132301

6 of 6

Sublimed polyoxystals

End Run 9 133404

Start Run 10 @ 240 134230

Below cloud generally but flying through
fall streaks.

End Run 10 135232

Start Run 11 135515

End 140510

Start Run 12 141058

End Run 12 142506

1443 - background error on CPI
- need to restart comp.

- Probe still not got by
- then it did
T now +2°C

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B116**

Date: 26/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS		N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	Y
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	N
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	Y
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B116

Date: 26/07/05

Instruments

1. Ozone – new instrument fitted pre-flight in place of SO₂. SO₂ constants on HORACE changed to show O₃ readings.
2. INU Panel – Status LED u/s
3. CCN – Wasn't cleaned at the end of B115, found to be full of water! Problem on initial transit couldn't resolve it so shut instrument down.
4. Video Recorder – Outboard (RFC) chewed up tape. Replaced at 1138Z.
5. CNC – Very high readings (10000) at high level initially, doesn't correlate with AMS CPC
6. Flight Manager's pc display locked up – rebooted pc then okay.

Status of other instruments

CPI – had to reboot PC several times in flight (in between runs). Possible problem with temperatures display at high level. No data lost on scientific runs.

Cloud Physics – SID 2 not working, PC reboots itself every 5 mins.

NO_x – fine, not much structure seen but that was expected for the levels we were flying

AMS, WAS, PAN, PtRms –all fine

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom H Calls – 1 by FAAM

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B116:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Keith Bower
CCN	No log seems to have been created for this flight
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
PAN	No log is taken/provided for PAN

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Rearward Facing Cameras

8mm video recordings from this flight reside with :
Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :
8mm video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :
Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :

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